

RADIASIYA TƏHLÜKƏSİZLİYİ PROBLEMLƏRİ: REGIONAL ASPEKTLƏR

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THERMAL CHARACTERIZATION OF POTTERY FRAGMENTS FROM NEOLITHIC SITES

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The methods of thermogravimetric (TG)/DTG and differential thermal analysis (DTA) are commonly used to study fired clay products, providing insight into the reactions occurring during firing and the properties of the raw materials used [1–4]. By analyzing changes in mass depending on temperature, these methods can reveal information about dehydration, dehydroxylation, and decomposition of minerals containing carbonate.

In this particular study, the thermal characterization of five pottery fragments from Neolithic sites was conducted using TG-DTA measurements, which were then used to estimate the firing temperature. The measurements were carried out using an SDA 6000 Temperature Scan with specific parameters.

Similarly, another study characterized ancient ceramic shards from an archaeological site in Azerbaijan, as well as two local raw ceramic pastes, using a combination of powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and thermal analysis techniques. The XRD analysis showed that all samples contained quartz, feldspar, and clay, with three out of four samples also containing calcite. The firing process was estimated to have stopped before 700°C based on the traditional approach, and the mass loss ratios indicated mild firing conditions. SEM analysis did not show signs of deep vitrification.

Overall, the combination of methods used in both studies suggests that the ceramics were made using similar manufacturing technology, but differences in the concentration of certain minerals

indicate differences in the sources of the investigated ceramic samples.

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